

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Accelerated Thermal Conductivity Testing of Aerogels with MTPS

The following Application Highlight features the use of the Modified Transient Plane Source method in the thermal conductivity testing of aerogels.

Aerogels represent a class of ultra-lightweight materials that are primarily composed of air (typically >99%). As a result, these materials have very high insulative capabilities (low thermal conductivity) and are extremely low density. Silica based aerogels are amongst the most common, however they can be made from a variety of materials. In application, aerogels can be applied for thermal insulation around critical components or in certain cases impregnated within a larger matrix to introduce better insulative performance, without sacrificing weight. Due to the novel characteristics of the material, it is important to have a way to properly characterize their performance.

Figure 1. Silica aerogel sample for MTPS sensor.

Thermal characterization of aerogels is often first attempted using steady-state methods such as Guarded-hot Plate (GHP) and/or Heat Flow Meter (HFM). While a powerful tool, steady-state methods add certain restrictions that can make sample preparation quite difficult. Most devices require samples ranging from 10-30 cm in length/width with thickness generally 5-10 mm or larger, in some cases an impossibility for experimental aerogels. These steady-state options are also limited in the environment state in which they can test, and measurements can take many hours to complete. These factors add some significant limitations for many groups looking to characterize their aerogels in ways that are truly representative to their application. For these reasons, C-Therm's Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) method is a great alternative to traditional steady-state methods. Requiring samples only 18 mm in diameter and 1-5 mm thick, the MTPS provides users a much more realistic option for testing aerogels. The MTPS can also be

placed in varying temperature, humidity, and atmospheric environments to allow for truly representative testing. Lastly, MTPS results can be collected in a matter of minutes, making it one of the fastest thermal characterization techniques available.

Figure 2. (Left) Trident configured with MTPS. (Right) pure silica aerogel (30mm diameter, 10mm thickness) being testing on MTPS.

Below highlights data collected on a variety of aerogel samples using the MTPS. Results were found to be within 4% of the specified values.

Figure 3. Thermal conductivity measurements of commercially available aerogels using the MTPS.

Special Consideration – Moisture Absorption

Regardless of method, when testing aerogels, it is important to understand their hygroscopic nature. If left uncontrolled, aerogels will absorb moisture which can alter structure, thermal performance, and visual qualities. From a thermal perspective, increased water content will have a detrimental influence on insulative performance. Water molecules will enter into the highly porous network and fill the voids, reducing air content and therefore increasing thermal conductivity. As such it is important to understand proper storage and conditioning for aerogels to avoid such issues. Alternatively, degradation can be prevented through the use of chemical treatments and coatings which will make the aerogel material hydrophobic in nature and prevent water absorption.

Below highlights an example data set of a semi-saturated aerogel material using the MTPS. Results were compared over a 7-day period to assess the change in thermal performance as a function of drying time.

Figure 4. An example of the effect of humidity on hydrophilic, non-coated aerogel samples' effective thermal conductivity.

Special Consideration – Density and Specific Heat Capacity

Specific to the MTPS, when testing thermal performance, the method often requires the manual input of density and specific heat capacity for the measurement of thermal conductivity. This input requirement is similar in nature to how traditional Laser Flash methods operate following ASTM E1461, however the thermal effusivity value is used in place of thermal diffusivity. Due to the extremely low

Figure 5. Fragile Aerogel Samples (30mm diameter).

density and relatively high specific heat, these input parameters are crucial to obtaining accurate thermal conductivity data for aerogel samples. Important to note, if density and heat capacity data is not available for the specific aerogel in question, thermal effusivity can be used as a guiding metric for comparison on a range of aerogel samples. Thermal conductivity and thermal effusivity will trend in a similar direction, allowing users to screen a multitude of samples for rapid characterization.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com